

Ethical Journalism versus Yellow Journalism: A Critical Reading of Film Ajmer 92

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Abstract

Women have received special respect in Indian society since ancient times. But from time to time, developments in society have tarnished the image of women in Indian society. A similar incident happened in the Ajmer 92 case. Rape and physical exploitation of hundreds of girl students have been depicted in this film. It is based on a true story that took place in Ajmer, Rajasthan. This film forces society to think about an important issue. The present study is qualitative in nature. In the presented research, a critical study has been done about incidents like rape happening in society, taking a film as the basis.

Keywords: Indian society, social journalism, crime, women, and social justice.

In the intricate tapestry of modern society, two seemingly disparate realms often intersect, generating a complex interplay of ethics, power, and truth. With the aid of limited and insufficient information, the creation of news and public discourse is a complex and conflicting process, rife with competing claims and conflicts for legitimacy and visibility (Konkes, 2023). Currently, a war is going on between ethical journalism and yellow journalism. Upon comprehensive examination of the domain of journalistic cinema, discernible patterns begin to surface. Certain films focus on individuals who are driven by a desire for recognition and employ journalism as a means to further their own ambitions (Sharma & Srivastava, 2024). Individuals adhere to the pursuit of financial gain and public recognition using any available methods, opting to engage in the practice of yellow journalism. However, it is important to acknowledge the presence of certain journalists who actively engage in ethical journalism, tirelessly advocating for the betterment of society. Responsible journalism entails the practice of ethical reporting, characterized by the absence of manipulation or bias (Bauer, 2017). The film *Ajmer 92* (Singh, 2023) encompasses a fascinating discourse that explores the compelling connection between the spectral world of criminal conspiracies, conflict, and journalism's unwavering pursuit of the truth. The film focuses on the conflict between ethical and yellow journalism.

Ajmer 92 is a gut-wrenching tale of families that were torn apart in the wake of unspeakable crimes of blackmailing and rape of over 250 college girls in Ajmer. Based on true incidents that took place in Ajmer in 1992, the plot revolves around Madhav (played by Karan Verma), a responsible reporter of a local newspaper, *Navkiran Samachar* and his love Geeta (played by Sumit Singh), daughter of Superintendent of Police (SP) Ranjit Singh (played by Rajesh Sharma). Mohan (played by Aakash Dahiya), another news reporter who runs a weekly tabloid *Toofan*. He is rotten to the core. He starts blackmailing girls after getting hold of their nude photos, threatening to publish them in the newspaper without masking. Geeta studies at a reputed college in the city. Once, her principal asked her to contact her father due to her poor attendance. During her attempts to rectify the situation, she confronts a politician named Yakub (played by Mahesh Balraj) who rapes her, and Yakub's sibling takes naked photographs of her. Yakub demands that Geeta bring her companion. He also rapes Geeta's companion and photographs her naked. In the interim, Mohan informs Madhav of the prominent figures behind

the network of nude photographs. Yakub's men later killed Mohan. It is now up to Madhav to identify the perpetrator.

In the background of the dramatic beginning scene, you can see a fort and a few mosque minarets. As the camera turns 180 degrees in the air, the blue skies of Ajmer, which is home to the Dargah of Moinuddin Chishti, turn dark because of a girl's frightening wail. The first scene shows what the story is all about. In the story that comes next, you'll learn about the horrible crime of assaulting and blackmailing women, the competition between two local journalists, and the never-ending search for justice (P. B. Sharma, 2023).

In this thought-provoking film, the conflict between yellow journalism and sensible journalism serves as a central theme in the first half, showcasing the influence and accountability of the media in shaping public perception. The New York Press coined the term "yellow journalism" in 1897 to denote the sensationalist coloring of the news (Donsbach, 2008).

Journalism, as the precursor of truth dissemination, is assigned the task of revealing stories that frame public perception and effect collective understanding. However, the quest of these stories often negotiates complex terrain marked by dissimilar perspectives, conferred interests, and inherent biases. As an outcome, conflicts can arise within the journalistic landscape, oscillating from ethical dilemmas within newsrooms to peripheral clashes encompassing sources, subjects, and audiences. As with all crime reporting, it is the duty of journalists to make sure that their work respects the victims' dignity and advances society as a whole (Konkes, 2023).

When Mohan publishes an explicit photograph of a college in his tabloid, Madhav is vehemently opposed. In addition, when Madhav meets the girl who has come to the police station to file a complaint against Mohan and discovers that Mohan is blackmailing her by threatening to publish her naked photographs in his tabloid *Toofan*, he writes about Mohan's wrongdoings in his newspaper. Madhav declines Mohan's offer to work together to uncover the syndicate responsible for the explicit photographs of college girls. He asserts that journalism has a social responsibility. Mohan, however, does not concur and is determined to turn it into a substantial income source. By threatening to publish the nude photos in his tabloid, he blackmails the girls and their family members. Madhav and Manoj's disagreements raise significant questions regarding the ethics of journalism (P. B. Sharma, 2023).

The complex interplay between the principles of integrity and objectivity and the reality of conflict presents journalists with both challenges and opportunities. Numerous journalistic shortcomings and failings are attributed to objective journalism; however, these criticisms are frequently erroneous because the journalists do not comprehend or define impartiality clearly (Ryan, 2001). This film is evidence of this. The film expertly depicts the journey of a journalist who advocates factual reporting, demonstrating that awareness is not merely a byproduct of journalism, but an essential function. Madhav began connecting the threads after Mohan's murder and uncovered a heinous criminal conspiracy in the city. He persuades SP Ranjit Singh to investigate the case with greater vigor and responsibility. He leaves no stone unturned to bring the truth to the public and the criminals on trial, whether by bringing evidence from Mohan's office or convincing the lab's owner to give over the evidence. Journalism's high standards are in jeopardy due to an ethical crisis. Economic and societal factors imperil the viability of journalism standards (Ward, 2010).

In the context of a sex scandal that occurred in Ajmer in 1992, the film explores the difficulties women face in the profoundly patriarchal setting of Indian society to survive. The female protagonists' encounter with these brutal realities highlights the complexities of their predicament, shedding light on the broader context of gender inequality. Numerous victims, driven to the verge of despair, committed suicide because of this case. The gravity of the situation highlights the significance of journalistic integrity when covering sensitive issues. The victims' trauma was exacerbated by the dissemination of their photographs and videos, a gruesome demonstration of the vileness of the exploitation.

In addition, the film emphasizes the concept of political and administrative helplessness, illustrating the frustration of those who struggle for justice in a system that often appears indifferent or obstructive. The journey of the female protagonist functions as a metaphor for this struggle, as she navigates the labyrinth of conspiracy and opportunistic public.

With a running time of 141 minutes, *Ajmer 92* (Singh, 2023) does a great job of capturing what it's like to be a girl and a parent of a girl in a culture that is afraid to speak the truth and stand up for the victims for fear of offending a particular group and sparking unrest (P. B. Sharma, 2023). In the film's initial scene, a girl is sexually assaulted. She informs her mother of this. Her mother assaults her and confines her inside the residence. The behavior of her own parents

shattered her heart, and she committed suicide by hanging herself. The fate of the other victims was identical. No assistance from parents, police, or the community. Additionally, the audience appeared opportunistic. Whoever obtained naked photographs began blackmailing the females. Everyone has their own justifications for being unable to assist the victims. Family members are preserving their sterling reputation. They appear to be very concerned about their daughters' prospective marriages. The police are reluctant to act against influential members of society. Government officials fear the Hindu-Muslim angle. To prevent the accused, Yakub (Mahesh Balraj), from turning this into a Hindu-Muslim litigation, Minister (Manoj Joshi) suggests including a Hindu as a defendant in the case. The family and society's neglect shattered the victims from the inside out. Six females, feeling helpless, committed suicide collectively.

At its core, the film beautifully illustrates journalism's role as a driving force for raising public awareness about the pursuit of justice. It portrays how, through meticulous investigation and unwavering determination, journalism can dismantle the walls of injustice and expose hidden truths.

Role of Journalism in exposing Ajmer exploitation and rape case

The Ajmer exploitation and rape case, which sent shockwaves through society, illustrates the power of journalism in unearthing scandalous crimes and holding the guilty accountable. The courageous actions of journalist Santosh Gupta, who dared to shed light on the grim reality through his report in the '*Dainik Navjyoti*' a daily newspaper, marked the beginning of a journey to justice.

Gupta's report, published in April 1992, brought to the forefront the unsettling exploitation of over a hundred college girls. The article revealed the horrifying details of how schoolgirls were ensnared, blackmailed, and subjected to sexual abuse. The mention of an intricate network involving influential individuals and the coercion of victims to entangle others in the racket painted a disturbing picture of systemic depravity. The journalistic intervention acted as a catalyst, prompting law enforcement to spring into action. The Ajmer exploitation case shows how journalism exposes hidden crimes and promotes a safer, more just society, despite its frequent criticism.

The case involving the exploitation scandal, which impacted over 100 girls, remains unresolved to this day. Despite the passage of time, justice has not been achieved, and the case is still pending in court. In 1998, a court in Ajmer handed life sentences to eight men, but the Rajasthan High Court acquitted four of them in 2001. The Supreme Court later reduced the sentences of the remaining four convicts to 10 years in 2003. Presently, six individuals are still undergoing trial.

The final scene of *Ajmer 92* (Singh, 2023) is heart-breaking. The brothers of Yakub, who are in hiding, call him. Yakub, who was given a life sentence in a mental asylum, is shown telling his brothers not to worry as he sits in a plush home. Burn all of them (the witnesses). This is even as the survivors are abandoned to their fate forever awaiting justice. The status quo continues to date (P. B. Sharma, 2023).

Corruption and investigative journalism

Corruption is a significant obstacle to development. It is the greatest impediment to the advancement of democratic institutions and principles, undermining and defying efforts made, particularly in developing nations (Kumar & Sharma, 2023). For years, Indian media have exposed government and business misbehavior, illegality, and corruption, sparking public indignation and reform. The Hindu's *Bofors Expose*, Tehelka's *Defence Deals Expose* and Indian Express's *Cement Scam Expose* are some of the most brilliant investigative practices in the history of Indian Journalism (Pal, 2017).

For India, the Bofors scandal that erupted in 1987 was a turning point. The Hindu discovered the issue, and Chitra Subramaniam-Duella and N. Ram covered it. Nearly 200 Bofors-related documents were obtained covertly, checked for accuracy, and translated from the Swedish language before being made public, along with interviews and insightful articles. This probe sparked such a public outcry that the incumbent administration ultimately came out on the losing side of the 1989 general election (Cinamon & Poel, 2023).

The findings of an undercover operation called 'Operation West End' were revealed by the media outlet *Tehelka* in 2001. Secret tapes of prominent politicians, government officials, and military officials accepting bribes from two reporters (posing as arms brokers) were made public. The ensuing uproar sparked a significant political storm and forced individuals implicated by the videotapes to resign (Pal, 2017).

On August 31, 1981, readers of the Indian Express awoke to a painstakingly researched expose on corruption in the awarding of government cement quotas, accompanied by supporting documentation and a scathing critique. The quick, brave, and non-lethal journalistic takeover is now recognized as India's Watergate, also known as the cement scandal (Pal, 2017).

Reel life portrayal of journalism in *Bollywood*

Bollywood movies' representations of real-life journalism frequently veer between idealistic pictures of brave reporters standing up for the truth and sensationalized dramatizations that emphasize melodrama and personal issues. In the past 13 years, at least six full-length movies about investigative reporting have been published in India, where intrusive journalists risked their lives to expose the shadowy side of politics, society, and crime (Kaushik & Pandey, 2023).

Movies like *Rang De Basanti* (Mehra, 2006) and *No One Killed Jessica* (Gupta, 2011) demonstrate how media can expose social injustices and encourage reform. These movies emphasize how crucial journalism is to exposing wrongdoing, fighting for justice, and empowering the public. *No One Killed Jessica* is based on the true story of the murder of Jessica Lall and the subsequent fight for justice by a journalist and Jessica's sister. The film highlights the power of media in exposing corruption and the struggle for women's rights.

Asian cinema's lens on journalism

Asian film has distinguished itself with its distinct narratives and unique storytelling approaches. Journalistic movies stand out as a dynamic force that offers insight and criticism on media, truth, and power dynamics in cultures. These films entertain and reflect the complex relationship between journalism, truth, and social conventions.

Vizontele (Erdogan & Sorak, 2001) is a Turkish film that focuses on the impact of television on a small village in Anatolia. The story revolves around a journalist who arrives in the village to cover the introduction of television and its effects on the community.

The Chinese film *12 Citizens* (Xu, 2014) adapts Reginald Rose's classic play '12 Angry Men' into a journalistic context. It focuses on a journalist who attempts to uncover the truth behind a murder trial and jury deliberations.

City of Life and Death (Lu, 2009) is a Chinese film is set during the Nanjing Massacre and follows a Western journalist as he documents the atrocities committed by Japanese soldiers. The film portrays the challenges of reporting amidst war and the moral dilemmas faced by journalists. *The Terror Live* (Kim, 2013) is a South Korean thriller that centres on a disgraced news anchor who receives a call from a terrorist demanding a live broadcast. The film unfolds as a tense negotiation between the journalist and the terrorist, with the truth at stake. *The Front Line* (Hun, 2011) is another South Korean film that revolves around a war correspondent stationed on the front lines during the Korean War. The film explores the psychological toll of reporting from the battlefield. By showcasing both the virtuous and darker sides of journalism, these movies encourage spectators to contemplate the critical choices journalists make and the impact of their decisions on the public's perception of reality.

Story is good but fails to leave good impression

On craft parameters, the film *Ajmer 92* fails to leave good impressions. Except for a few shots, the cinematography is average; it could be better, as *Ajmer* is a very beautiful city surrounded by mountains and lakes. The casting needs much attention, as the film subject is bold and sensible. In this regard, actors should have chosen who transforms emotions with dialogue on the screen. Almost all actors seem flat for being emotive on the screen and delivering dialogue. The background music is too loud and seems to compensate for the performance deficiencies of the actors. The movie skillfully avoids emphasizing the perpetrators' connections to the *Sufi Dargah* while remaining authentic to the actual events. The movie succeeds in holding the audience's interest the entire time. One can only speculate how different the experience may have been if the worry and anxiety had been expertly expressed through facial expressions rather than solely relying on a loud background score.

The Hindu community, which is separated along caste lines, is shown in *Ajmer 92* (Singh, 2023) to be weak, while having strong basic beliefs, particularly when surrounded by radicals and fundamentalists with criminal intent. This is another admirable but somewhat concealed message. On the other hand, the Modi-led government of India is planning to save the girl child in the country. The Union government has started the *Beti Bachao-Beti Padhao* campaign to save the girl child (Parmar & Sharma, 2020).

Conclusion

Received: 2 July 2024

Revised: 13 July 2024

Accepted: 30 July 2024

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Ajmer 92 (Singh, 2023) maintains its integrity in its storytelling, but it falters when the script demands more in-depth investigation. There is a need for a more in-depth investigation of the case because some episodes come out as shallow. The film manages to keep up a steady pace and see it through to the end, successfully engrossing audiences and grabbing their interest. Despite its shortcomings, it undoubtedly has an influence on the audience.

This investigation illuminates the moral conundrums that confront journalists when they learn about and report on criminal schemes, but it also focuses on the wider implications for openness, accountability, and the delicate balance between protecting the public interest and maintaining the integrity of investigative journalism. Understanding the significance of this interconnected dynamic requires a journey into the ethical grey area, where the revelation of a criminal conspiracy can both serve as a journalistic coup and as a catalyst for significant conflicts of interest.

It is impossible to ignore the film's relevance in a contemporary socioeconomic setting. This film highlights the seriousness of women's assault as a horrible crime that is capable of destroying the lives of victims, especially in light of the Manipur tragedy, which is making headlines in the media. Karan Verma and Sumit Singh, the lead performers, fall short of the caliber of the supporting ensemble, which has brilliant actors like Rajesh Sharma, Sayaji Shinde, and Manoj Joshi. The portrayal of Karan is shallow and leaves no lasting impression. Despite this flaw, the movie continues to be a vital and contemporary example of how crucial it is to defend women's rights and work for justice for those who have been victims of such heinous crimes.

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